

Effect of Bioneema and Nitrogenous Fertilizer on Growth Parameters, Drymatter Content, Yield attributes and Availability of Nutrients in Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill) C.V. Money Maker

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Abstract:- A field trial was displayed in (1x1 Sq.M.) micro plots during winter season (2008-09 and 2009-10) to study effect of neem product Bioneem and nitrogenous fertilizer (Urea) on growth, dry matter no. of tomato fruits, yield and nutrients availability. Experiment was conducted in factorial randomized block design (RBD) by varying levels of Bioneema (viz., B₀ (control), B₃, (20 Kg^{ha⁻¹}), B₂ (40 Kg^{ha⁻¹}), and B₁ (60 Kg^{ha⁻¹}) and Nitrogen N. (Control) N, (50 Kg^{ha⁻¹}) and N₂ (100 Kg^{ha⁻¹}). It is quite obvious that treatment B₂N₁ (40 kg Bioneema + 50 Kg^{ha⁻¹} N) through Urea brought about significant improvement in height, No of branches of tomato plants at various successive stages in (2008-09 and 2009-2010) at 90 DAT where B₃N, (T₁₀) significantly enhanced the no. of branches. It is further revealed that treatment T₈ (B₂N) registered a tremendous increase in Drymatter % in first year while T₁₀ (B₃N₀) showed better result in second year. Likewise T₁₂(B₃N₂) significantly increased the no. of fruits while T₁₁ (B₃N₁) enhanced in second year. The Treatment T₉ (B₂N₂) responded well in enhancing the fruit yield in first year whereas T₃ (B₀N₂) improved the fruit yield (5-11 Kg. per plot). The uptake of nutrients i.e. N, Protein, P, Mg and Fe contents in general influenced significantly by bioneema and nitrogenous fertilizer (Urea). The uptake of nutrients was virtually higher in tomato plants of B₂N₂ and B₃N₁treatments in first year than that of second year.

It is inferred from the foregoing observations that less amount of N fertilizer along with Neem product is quite beneficial for plants growth, yield as well as disease resistance.

Keyword:- Bioneema, Nitrogenous fertilizer, Drymatter, Yield, attributes, *Lycopersicon esculentum*, Nutrients.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tomato (*Lycopersicon*, *esculentum*, Mill) is one of the most popular and widely grown vegetable in the world ranking second in importance to potato in many countries Fageria et al (2003). India is the second largest producer of Tomato in the world after China, accounting for about 11% of the world tomato Production Anonymous (2011). Tomato is a rich source of Vit-A, Vit-C and lycopene. Because of its high nutritive value, it has great demand as raw, cooked and processed vegetable. A number of

processed products like paste, puree, soup, juice, ketchup, drinks, whole peeled tomatoes etc. are prepared on large scale and used as food ingredients Kalloo (1991). Thus, today it is one of the important raw materials for multimillion food industry. Besides nutritional importance tomato also has great medicinal value. Consumption of tomato fruits helps in the prevention of cancer and heart diseases because of antioxidant properties of Lycopene Kaur et al (2013).

Neem products with or without azadirachtin has shown excellent pest control action against infestation by over three hundred insect, pest and infection by nematode, viruses and some pathogenic fungus. Neem cultivation has been taken up over 160 countries registered in both in India as well as abroad.

India has a rich heritage on Neem (*Azadirachta indica*), It is a native of the Indian subcontinent and is highly esteemed tree for the people in the region. Neem has multifarious effects viz antifidant, repellent, toxicant, insect growth inhibitor and antibiopasitory against insects and pests.

The soil amendment with Neem cake and green manuring with Neem leaves were deleterious to various plant parasite nematodes which causes severe losses in tomato. All these reports are considered as a source of multiple pesticide; with these diversified mode and spectrum of action Neem offer an ideal pesticide which is also safe to environment and other natural enemies or pests.

Nitrification retarding studies some Neem compound viz azadirachtin, Nimbin Solanin etc. and new active constituents epinimbin and bioneem as the Key nitrification retarder. since nitrification inhibitory effect on neem Cake is well established. It is usefully employed in increasing the efficiency of urea.

Urea is the most important and widely used fertilizer. It is highly concentrated organic nitrogenous containing 46% N in amide form, 20 percent Carbon, 26.6% oxygen and 6.7% of hydrogen.

Several workers have studied the effect of Bioneema and urea on various growth parameters, yield and Nutrients uptake in tomato but very meagre information are available on this aspect. Keeping these facts in view, the present study

was undertaken to evaluate the effect of Bioneema and urea as nitrogenous fertilizer.

II. MATERIAL AND METHOD

A field experiment was carried out in micro plots having size of (1×1 Sq.m.) at experimental site St. John's College, Agra during winter season. The test crop Moneymaker was transplanted on 15 Nov., 2008 at evening time at a distance of 50 cm plant to plant and 50 cm row to row. The micro plots used for experimental work had soil pH (1.2.5) soil water suspension ECE (dsm⁻¹) at 25°C 1.15% organic carbon, 0.35 available N 185 Kg^{ha}⁻¹, P₂O₅, K₂O 180 Kg^{ha}⁻¹, 14.0 Kg^{ha}⁻¹, and Zinc 0.85 mg Kg⁻¹. The experiment was laid out in factorial randomised block design with three replications of twelve treatments.

The four levels of Bioneema 0.0 (B₀), B₁ (20 Kg^{ha}⁻¹), B₂ (40 Kg^{ha}⁻¹) and B₃ (60 Kg^{ha}⁻¹) and three levels of Nitrogen through urea viz N₀ (control), N₁ (50 Kg^{ha}⁻¹) and N₂ (100 Kg^{ha}⁻¹) were used. After dividing the experimental area in 36 micro plots the recommended doze of fertilizer (urea) and Bioneema were mixed before transplanting the seedlings. The recommended doze of N, P, K through urea S.S.P. and Muriate of Potash were applied in experimental plots before transplanting the seedlings. Rest half doze of N through urea was top dressed before flowering the test crop. The crop was irrigated as and when required. The growth parameters at different intervals i.e. 30, 45, 60, 90 DAT in both the years were recorded. The no. of fruits / plot, yield of tomato per plot and drymatter at maturity stage were observed. The plant samples were collected from each plot for the analysis of N, protein, P, Mg, Fe uptake.

The height (cm) of the plant from ground level was recorded at 30, 45, 60 and 90 days after transplanting in both the trails for this purpose two plants were randomly selected from each plot and tagged for further observations, Similarly no. of branches of tomato under different treatment were also done in the same manner as that of previous one. Drymatter accumulation Green herbage from plot by plot were collected and fresh weight was taken and then kept in oven maintained at 105°C for 8 hrs. The dried herbage was then weighed after cooling. The difference in weight between the green herbage and dried matter accumulation was recorded. The no. of fruits and yield of tomato was recorded at maturity level. After tomato crop; five random plants samples were taken out and dried and analysed for various nutrients. P in plant was estimated by adopting vanadomolybdate yellow colour method **Jackson (1973)** Nitrogen in plant was determined by using modified Kjeldahl method. The uptake of nutrients was calculated on the basis of yield and content of nutrients. Ca was estimated by flame photometer and Fe was determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The data (Table 1) pertaining to growth parameter (height of plant and no. of branches) at various successive stages / intervals as affected by varying levels of Bioneema and Nitrogenous fertilizer (Urea) clearly indicated that height of tomato plants under the influence of neem product

(Bioneema) and urea showed a remarkable increase in height and no. of branches before flowering stage. The treatment T₀ (B₂N₂) increased the height of plants to the extent of (87.0 cm) in 1st yr, and (59.6 cm.) in second year (2009-2010). The higher application of bioneema and nitrogen (B₃N₂) did not influence appreciably on the height of plants (1st yr.) as well as second year. The reason for enhancement in the height of plants due to Bioneema and nitrogen may help in elongation which protects, the plant from various insect and diseases. These results also corroborate the findings of Das and Patro (1990), Mozarkat (1991), who also conducted and reported that application of PGR increased the growth of plants. The effect reduced plant growth it is surprising to note that the height bit some extent (58.6 cm) in year. The no. of branches increased with the rise in Bioneema and nitrogen levels over control. Probably this may due to the cell division and growth which is owing to the presence of Neem Product and Nitrogen as basal application Kar (1985), also observed similar findings

Data presented in (Table 2) pertaining to drymatter accumulation (%), No. of fruits and yield of tomato found significantly over control at B₂N₁. The higher concentration of Bioneema and nitrogen did not encourage to grow more drymatter content. It is further revealed from the data that average yield of tomato fruits with application of Bioneema and nitrogen clearly showed that fruit yield significantly increased over rest of the treatments. Beyond the treatment B₃N₂ the yield declined. The highest yield recorded at T₉ (B₂N₂) in first year (6.68 Kg/Plot and 5.11 Kg./Plot) which is slightly reduced in second year (2009-2010). The Similar findings also showed by **Dostal and Wileax (1971)**.

It is obvious from the data depicted in Table 3 that. N uptake significantly increased with increasing level of Bioneema and Nitrogenous fertilizer (urea). The N uptake increased from 0.106 (Control) to the extent of (0.214)% at T₈(B₂N₁) in first year whereas in second year it enhanced from 0.101% (control) to (0.209%) at B₂N₂. Similarly in protein content increased from 0.588% (B₃N₂) in first year and enhanced upto 1.096 (B₃N₀) at T₁₀ in second year. It is interested to note that increasing level of Bioneema and N level the N uptake tremendously reduced over control. It is evident from the findings that Neem product enhanced the N fixation which acted as good N inhibitor Reddy and Prasad (1977), Das and Padhi (1991) and Das and Patro (1990).

It is quite obvious from the results pertaining to protein that B₁N₀ treatment enhanced the protein. The antagonistic effect of Nitrogen over Bioneema was found to superior and showed better result in second year (2009-2010). It is further revealed that P uptake increased with increasing level of Bioneema and Nitrogen (Urea). The P content observed highest at B₂N₂ levels is both the year but, P uptake was higher in first year than of second year. P in also responsible for bringing the maturity in plants Application of 60 Kg^{ha}⁻¹ Bionemma and 100 Kg N through urea tended to enhance the Mg uptake in tomato plant while it reduced in first year. This reduction in Mg may be due to the hindrance caused by increased concentration of Na ions in the absorption and translocation of Mg from the roots to the above ground parts. No particular trend in increasing or decreasing manner

could be observed. Mg is very important secondary plant nutrients from the growth and health of plant which is present in the Chlorophyll plant pigment. **David and Winsor (1967)**.

It is evident from the results presented in Table 3 that Fe uptake increased significantly over control with the rise in Neem product and Nitrogen levels. The highest uptake of Fe increased at B₂N₂ (40 Kg) Bioneema + 100 kg N and Fe

concentration reduced after higher application of Bioneema and urea in both the years.

The results of this study leads to a conclusion that Bioneema a Neem product and nitrogenous fertilizer (urea) had remarkable effect on all the parameters. But above all B₂N₂ treatment found to be the most superior in the first year than that of second year.

Treatment		Height of Plant (Cm)								Number of Branches							
		2008-2009				2009-2010				2008-2009				2009-2010			
		30 DAT	45 DAT	60 DAT	90 DAT	30 DAT	45 DAT	60 DAT	90 DAT	30 DAT	45 DAT	60 DAT	90 DAT	30 DAT	45 DAT	60 DAT	90 DAT
T ₁	B ₀ N ₀	10.0	16.3	29.6	69.6	09.0	14.7	21.0	43.6	3.6	6.6	86	13.6	2.6	3.3	4.3	6.6
T ₂	B ₀ N ₁	13.0	20.6	37.0	78.3	11.6	17.0	24.0	46.0	3.5	7.3	10.3	15.3	4.6	5.3	6.3	8.0
T ₃	B ₀ N ₂	14.0	22.0	38.0	79.3	12.3	17.6	24.6	48.3	5.2	7.3	10.3	14.6	4.3	5.3	6.3	8.0
T ₄	B ₁ N ₀	13.0	20.6	37.0	78.6	12.0	16.0	21.3	43.0	5.0	7.2	10.3	15.6	3.6	4.3	6.0	7.0
T ₅	B ₁ N ₁	15.0	23.0	38.3	80.6	13.0	18.0	25.6	48.3	5.6	7.6	10.6	15.3	4.6	5.3	6.6	8.0
T ₆	B ₂ N ₀	14.6	21.0	38.6	80.5	13.6	17.6	25.5	48.6	5.5	7.6	10.6	15.3	4.3	5.3	6.3	8.0
T ₇	B ₂ N ₁	14.5	22.5	38.3	80.3	12.5	18.3	27.3	50.6	5.3	7.3	10.3	15.3	4.3	5.0	6.3	8.6
T ₈	B ₂ N ₂	19.6	29.3	45.6	87.0	16.6	21.6	29.6	59.6	7.3	9.3	12.3	17.0	5.6	6.8	7.8	9.0
T ₉	B ₃ N ₀	18.0	27.0	40.2	80.3	15.0	20.6	28.3	57.3	5.6	7.6	10.6	15.0	4.6	4.6	5.6	7.0
T ₁₀	B ₃ N ₁	14.	27.0	40.1	81.5	12.6	18.0	27.3	59.0	5.0	8.0	11.0	16.0	5.3	6.6	7.6	10.0
T ₁₁	B ₃ N ₂	18.3	22.6	39.3	81.0	15.3	19.3	21.3	57.0	5.3	7.3	10.3	15.3	3.4	5.3	6.0	8.0
T ₁₂		17.0	26.6	39.6	81.6	14.5	21.0	28.8	57.6	6.0	8.3	11.0	16.0	5.0	6.0	7.0	9.0
CD at 5%		3.13	2.71	1.59	1.37	6.89	5.96	7.86	7.80	0.59	0.51	0.013	0.012	0.16	0.26	1.89	1.75

Table 1: Effect of varying Levels of Bioneema and Nitrogenous fertilizer on different growth Parameters in Tomato

Treatment		Dry Matter (%)		Number of Fruits		Yield of Fruits/Pot (Kg)	
		2008-09	2009-10	2008-09	2009-10	2008-09	2009-10
T ₁	B ₀ N ₀	15.37	12.44	33.3	27.3	2.25	1.46
T ₂	B ₀ N ₁	14.32	13.17	40.0	32.0	6.24	3.34
T ₃	B ₀ N ₂	16.35	13.55	40.0	33.6	6.46	5.11
T ₄	B ₁ N ₀	15.89	12.33	40.6	33.3	3.64	3.45
T ₅	B ₁ N ₁	17.10	13.41	41.6	33.3	4.75	4.76
T ₆	B ₁ N ₂	13.89	12.13	42.6	33.3	4.38	3.49
T ₇	B ₂ N ₀	14.67	13.55	41.3	37.0	4.38	3.78
T ₈	B ₂ N ₁	19.45	14.44	44.0	40.6	5.41	3.83
T ₉	B ₂ N ₂	16.03	14.63	44.0	42.3	6.68	2.78
T ₁₀	B ₃ N ₀	14.42	15.40	41.0	38.6	4.71	3.64
T ₁₁	B ₃ N ₁	15.53	15.33	44.3	42.6	4.66	1.97
T ₁₂	B ₃ N ₂	14.50	14.98	44.6	40.6	3.31	5.00
CD at 5%		17.83	20.58	0.301	0.188	0.348	0.218

Table 2: Showing the effect of different Levels of Bioneema and Nitrogenous Fertilizer (Urea) on drymatter No. of Fruits and Fruits Yield.

Treatment		N Uptake (%)		Protein (%)		P Uptake mg/100 mg		Mg Content in Plant Mg/100 g		Fe Content mg/100g	
T ₁	B ₀ N ₀	0.106	0.101	0.590	0.453	130.33	148.33	111.75	119.72	16.35	18.22
T ₂	B ₀ N ₁	0.125	0.112	0.715	0.601	137.00	167.66	128.13	130.67	12.98	20.04
T ₃	B ₀ N ₂	0.195	0.172	1.007	1.010	157.33	178.66	123.85	127.12	19.46	24.33
T ₄	B ₁ N ₀	0.196	0.163	1.376	0.923	082.33	154.33	130.65	137.53	20.13	25.56
T ₅	B ₁ N ₁	0.157	0.151	0.786	1.039	104.00	172.33	129.28	150.72	21.41	26.14
T ₆	B ₁ N ₂	0.134	0.172	0.744	0.801	106.33	191.0	133.51	149.33	25.30	31.26
T ₇	B ₂ N ₀	0.195	0.132	0.689	1.090	127.66	157.00	129.56	135.92	20.56	21.54
T ₈	B ₂ N ₁	0.214	0.190	1.070	0.974	113.00	166.66	130.29	171.88	22.60	22.46
T ₉	B ₂ N ₂	0.145	0.209	1.220	0.786	146.33	196.33	129.87	165.14	24.62	28.30
T ₁₀	B ₃ N ₀	0.131	0.140	0.745	1.096	119.66	166.33	128.35	158.64	19.63	21.49
T ₁₁	B ₃ N ₁	0.128	0.146	0.716	0.736	130.33	166.66	133.82	152.21	21.34	25.83
T ₁₂	B ₃ N ₂	0.133	0.139	0.588	0.931	131.66	185.00	130.28	183.64	20.43	23.67
CD at 5%		1.53	1.54	2.67	2.86	1.56	1.59	2.16	1.86	3.56	3.27

Table 3: N, Protein (%) P, Mg and iron uptake as Affected by varying levels of Neem Product (Bioneema) and Nitrogenous fertilizer (Urea) in two successive years

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